

FAAM facility for airborne atmospheric measurements

FLIGHT FOLDER

Flight No. B442
 Date: 30 Apr 2009
 Take Off: 05:00:46Z
 Landing: 09:15:40Z
 Flight Time 4h 14m 54s

Campaign: MEVEX Maritime Flight 4
Operating Area: Ocean, E of Oman

POB	Position	Name	Institute	Logs y/n
1	Captain	Alan Foster	Directflight	
2	Co-pilot	Luc Lathouwers	Directflight	
3	CCM	Gaynor Ottaway	Directflight	
4	Mission Scientist	Dave Pollard	Met Office	
5	Flight Manager	Steve Devereau	FAAM	
6	Core Chem / AVAPS	Kate Turnbull	FAAM	
7	Cloud Physics	Martyn Pickering	Met Office	
8	ARIES	Stuart Rogers	Met Office	
9	SWS / SHIMS	Martin Glew	Met Office	
10	Wet Neph / CVI / IIR	Andy Wilson	Met Office	
11	MARSS	James Bowles	Met Office	
12	Mission Scientist 2	Jon Taylor	Met Office	
13	Mini-LIDAR	Joss Kent	Met Office	
14	Observer	Dave Membury	Met Office	
15				
16				
17				
18				
19				

Missing Log Sheet	Reason
Pre-flight log	No log available
ViRC chat log	No log available / ViRC not used
Brief	Sortie brief yet to be added
De-brief	Sortie De-brief yet to be created by ???
Core Chemistry / TDLAS	no In Flight log except in cases of instrument problems
PSAP log	No log as PSAP pump/filter info included on Flight Summary page
Wet Neph	No log passed to FAAM yet
CVI	No log passed to FAAM yet
SWS / SHIMS	No log passed to FAAM yet
Mini-Lidar	No log passed to FAAM yet
IIR	No IIR log is provided for the Flight Folder

Revision	Date	Author	Comments
r0	31 Dec 2009	Doug Anderson	Initial version missing the above noted logs
r1			
r2			

VIDEO RECORDINGS:

The following avi format video recordings should be available at the BADC in core_processed/faam-video :

faam-video-dfc_faam_20090430_r0_b442_072302_1hz.avi
 faam-video-dfc_faam_20090430_r0_b442_082231_1hz.avi

faam-video-ffc_faam_20090430_r0_b442_053234_1hz.avi
 faam-video-ffc_faam_20090430_r0_b442_063234_1hz.avi
 faam-video-ffc_faam_20090430_r0_b442_072254_1hz.avi
 faam-video-ffc_faam_20090430_r0_b442_082226_1hz.avi

faam-video-rfc_faam_20090430_r0_b442_053237_1hz.avi
 faam-video-rfc_faam_20090430_r0_b442_063237_1hz.avi
 faam-video-rfc_faam_20090430_r0_b442_072257_1hz.avi
 faam-video-rfc_faam_20090430_r0_b442_082228_1hz.avi

faam-video-ufc_faam_20090430_r0_b442_053758_1hz.avi
 faam-video-ufc_faam_20090430_r0_b442_063758_1hz.avi
 faam-video-ufc_faam_20090430_r0_b442_072305_1hz.avi

FLIGHT SUMMARY

Flight No B442
 Date: 30/04/2009
 Project: MEVEX (Maritime)
 Location: Oman

Start Time	End Time	Event	Height (s)	Hdg	Comments
----	----	-----	-----	---	-----
044540		Start-Up	0.14 kft	266	
044811		power c/o	0.14 kft	267	
045006		taxy	0.14 kft	266	
045546		start pirouette	0.15 kft	277	
045846		stop pirouette	0.16 kft	273	
045921		open asp	0.15 kft	357	
050046		T/O	4.4 kft	081	Muscat
050601		BBR	6.3 kft	081	retract
051103		JW	14.4 kft	103	zero
052052	054438	Profile 1	21.0 - 0.18 kft	108	
053308		Video	8.1 kft	108	recording
053842		!	3.0 kft	173	500fpm
054857	060315	Run 1.1	0.61 - 0.67 kft	062	sea state 4
060548	062145	Run 2.1	1.2 - 1.1 kft	264	
060644		Heimann	1.1 kft	260	cal
062518	063853	Run 3.1	3.1 kft	077	
064232	064951	Run 4.1	5.0 kft	267	
064413		Heimann	5.0 kft	265	cal
065323	070110	Run 4.2	5.0 kft	068	
070520		Heimann cal	3.1 kft	261	
070543	070920	Run 5.1	3.1 kft	252	
071247	071435	Run 6.1	0.60 - 0.71 kft	023	
072403	073239	Run 7.1	5.1 kft	068	
073615	074231	Run 7.2	5.1 kft	257	
074536	075237	Run 7.3	5.1 kft	061	
075859	080645	Profile 2	0.28 - 8.0 kft	232	
080854	081827	Profile 2	8.1 - 18.0 kft	067	
082031	082603	Profile 2	18.0 - 24.0 kft	256	
082604	083342	Sonde 01	24.0 kft	254	
082709		TWC	24.0 kft	271	evap 2 on
091540		Land	0.21 kft	176	Muscat
091728		pirouette	0.21 kft	266	
092034		pirouette	0.21 kft	266	
091728		ASP	0.21 kft	266	closed
092354		Shutdown	0.21 kft	266	23 35.36N 58 17.66E
092406		power c/o	0.21 kft	266	

B442 02:42:59-09:33:48

GLNG_PARA0581, GLAT_PARA0580

Mission Scientist's Log

MEVEX
WAVE SORTIE
Miss Sci 2 leg.

Flight No B 442 Date 30 APR 09 Name Jon Taylor Page 1 of 2

Time (GMT)	Run / Profile	Height	Hdg	GPS Position	Remarks / Observations (cloud type & amount in oktas, weather, visibility, winds, sea state etc.) eg Cirrus 2/8, StratoCu 3/8, hazy, wind 240°/24kts
045550					Pirouette. start Hdg 270.
045844					Pirouette End
					climb out - several tops at approx 12500 ft surface wind per 050 but from 700 ft and above is 260
052052	P1	FL 210 ↓	109		start of P1 descent reph showed low at 2000 ft + thin layer at 18500 then main layer 15000 to approx. 5000 ft ↓ 3000 ft shows sig O ₃ structure
054638	P1	100 ft	055	22°18'N 61°18'E	End of P1 wind is 200 kts at alt 100 ft wind 012 m/s / 27k. Aerial optical depth ≈ 0.3
054857	P1.1	600 ft	060	22°30'N 61°18'E	st Run P1.1 to pass ahead ship. XXXXXXXXXXXXXXXXXXXXXXXXXXXX PCASP ≈ 700/cc reph ≈ 80 · 10 ⁻⁶ m ⁻¹ Scheer ≈ 877 W·m ⁻² XXXXXXXXXXXXXXXXXXXXXXXXXXXX
0559					wake off to right - ≈ 5° from ship
060022					XXXXXXXXXXXX Overload ship ≈ 10C = ?
060315	P1.1	600 ft			End Run 1.1 climb to 1000 ft
060360					level 1000 ft.
060548	P2.1	100 ft	261	22°08'N 62°18'E	st Run 2.1 to cross ship from bow to stern

Cloud Physics Flight Log B442

Date: 30/04/09	Operator: MAP	DRS Time: 02:45:00	DAU1 Time: +0	DAU2 Time: +0	AUX1 Time: +0	AUX2 Time: +0
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DAU2 Disk space?

	PCASP SPP-200		CDP		PCASP		2DC		FFSSP		SID3	
Operated?												NO
Pre-flight checks	Vref	7.5	Ref V (~3):	2.64	Vref (>7):	Unknown	El#1 V (>1):	-1.7	Ref V:	3.5	Comms?	No
	Sample flow	1.34			Flow (~1):	0.65	El#32 V (>1):	-1.7				
	Sheath flow	16.8			Pressure:	1008						
					Temp (NDIT)	33.7						

GMT	Height	CDP		PCASP SPP-200		PCASP		2DC		Habit	FFSSP	SID3	Comments
		#/cc	MVD	#/cc	MVD	#/cc	Mean R	#/L	Max R				
03:25:00													Pecan & 50 microns pre-flight cal for FFSSP
03:30:00													10 and 20 microns pre-flight cal for CDP
05:10:00													Old PCASP heater on
05:13:00													Heaters on
05:20:52	FL210			100	0.2	30	0.07				30		Start Profile 1
05:21:50	FL200			80	0.2	30	0.07						
05:22:45	FL190			100	0.2	60	0.07						
05:23:50	FL180			120	0.2	75	0.06						
05:24:58	FL170			100	0.2	50	0.06						
05:25:50	FL160			100	0.2	40	0.06						
05:26:39	FL150			100	1	80	0.06				31		
05:27:40	FL140			100	1	95	0.08						
05:28:26	FL130	0.1	4	200	1	350	0.10						
05:29:30	FL120	0.2	8	450	1	500	0.10						
05:30:16	FL110	0.2	8	500	1	480	0.10						
05:31:03	FL100	0.2	8	500	1	550	0.10						
05:32:11	FL090	0.2	8	500	1	540	0.10				32		
05:33:13	FL080	0.2	8	500	1.5	580	0.10						
05:34:20	FL070	0.2	8	400	1.5	550	0.10				33		
05:35:20	FL060	0.2	8	500	1.5	630	0.10				35		
05:36:22	FL050	0.2	8	450	1.5	650	0.10						
05:37:30	FL040	0.2	8	500	1.5	700	0.10				36		
05:38:36	FL030	0.2	7	450	1.5	650	0.10						

GMT	Height	CDP		PCASP SPP-200		PCASP		2DC		Habit	FFSSP	SID3	Comments
		#/cc	MVD	#/cc	MVD	#/cc	Mean R	#/L	Max R				
05:40:41	FL020	0.2	7	450	1.5	660	0.10				37		Heaters off
05:42:55	FL010	0.2	5	400	1.5	600	0.10				38		
05:44:40	100'	0.2	7	350	1.5	510	0.09						End of Profile
05:48:58	600'												Start Run 1
05:49:00		0.2	7	600	1.5	610	0.09				40		
05:51:00		0.15	7	600	1.5	640	0.09				41		
05:53:00		0.2	7	600	1	650	0.09				42		
05:55:00		0.2	7	600	1	660	0.09				43		
05:57:00		0.2	7	600	1	670	0.09				46		
05:59:00		0.2	7	650	1.5	630	0.09				48		
06:01:00		0.2	7	650	1.5	630	0.09						
06:03:00		0.2	7	650	1.5	625	0.09						
06:03:15													End of run
06:05:47	1000'												Start Run 2
06:06:00		0.3	5	600	1.5	660	0.09				49		
06:08:00		0.3	5	650	1.5	640	0.09				50		
06:10:00		0.3	7	600	1.5	630	0.09						
06:12:00		0.3	7	600	1.5	650	0.09				51		
06:14:00		0.3	7	600	1.5	620	0.09				52		
06:16:00		0.3	7	650	1.5	600	0.09				52		
06:18:00		0.2	7	600	1.5	610	0.09						
06:20:00		0.2	7	600	1.5	600	0.09				53		
06:21:45													End of Run
06:2522	3000'												Start Run 3
06:26:00		0.2	7	650	1.5	510	0.10				55		
06:28:00		0.2	7	700	2	570	0.10						
06:30:00		0.2	7	650	1.5	570	0.10				56		
06:32:00		0.2	7	650	1.5	640	0.09						
06:34:00		0.3	7	700	1.5	570	0.10				57		
06:36:00		0.4	7	650	1.5	590	0.09				58		
06:38:00		0.4	7	650	1.5	560	0.09				59		
06:38:56													End of Run
06:42:31	5000'												Start Run 4.1
06:43:00		0.4	7	650	1.5	510	0.09				60		
06:45:00		0.4	7	650	1.5	520	0.09						
06:47:00		0.4	7	640	1.5	540	0.09				61		

GMT	Height	CDP		PCASP SPP-200		PCASP		2DC		Habit	FFSSP	SID3	Comments
		#/cc	MVD	#/cc	MVD	#/cc	Mean R	#/L	Max R				
06:49:00		0.4	7	600	1.5	530	0.10				62		
06:49:51													End of Run
06:53:27	5000'												Start Run 4.2
06:54:00		0.4	7	600	1.5	500	0.10				64		
06:56:00		0.4	7	600	1.5	500	0.09						
06:58:00		0.3	7	600	1.5	500	0.09						
07:00:00		0.3	7	600	1.5	450	0.09				65		
07:01:11													End of Run
07:05:46	3000'												Start Run 5.1
07:06:00		0.3	7	600	1.5	550	0.10				67		
07:08:00		0.3	7	600	1.5	590	0.10				68		
07:09:20													End of Run
07:12:38	600'												Start Run 6.1
07:13:00		0.3	7	600	1.5	680	0.09				69		
07:14:38													End of Run
07:15:08	1000'	0.3	7	650	1.5	600	0.09				70		Start P2
07:16:00	FL020	0.3	7	600	1.5	550	0.09						
07:16:55	FL030	0.3	7	500	1.5	450	0.09				71		
07:17:46	FL040	0.3	7	600	1.5	430	0.10						
07:18:46	FL050	0.3	7	500	1.5	400	0.10						End of Profile
07:24:04	5000'												Start Run 7.1
07:25:00		0.3	7	600	1.5	510	0.10				73		
07:27:00		0.3	7	600	1.5	520	0.10				74		
07:29:00		0.3	7	600	1.5	450	0.10				75		
07:31:00		0.3	7	650	1.5	550	0.10						
07:32:37													End of Run
07:36:06	5000'												Start Run 7.2
07:37:00		0.5	7	650	1.5	520	0.10				77		
07:39:00		0.5	10	600	1.5	520	0.10				78		
07:41:00		0.4	10	600	1.5	500	0.10				79		
07:42:30													End of Run
07:45:56	5000'												Start Run 7.3
07:46:00		0.4	10	600	1.5	500	0.10				80		
07:48:00		0.4	10	650	1.5	500	0.10				81		
07:50:00		0.4	10	600	1.5	500	0.10				82		
07:52:38													End of Run

GMT	Height	CDP		PCASP SPP-200		PCASP		2DC		Habit	FFSSP	SID3	Comments
		#/cc	MVD	#/cc	MVD	#/cc	Mean R	#/L	Max R		Blocks Tx	Counts	
07:58:55	100'	0.3	7	600	1.5	550	0.10				85		Start Profile 3
07:59:47	FL010	0.5	7	600	1.5	500	0.10				86		
08:00:38	FL020	0.4	7	600	2	510	0.10						
08:01:32	FL030	0.5	7	600	2	480	0.10						
08:02:30	FL040	0.4	7	700	2	430	0.10						
08:03:35	FL050	0.4	7	600	2	400	0.10				87		
08:04:35	FL060	0.3	7	600	2	370	0.10						
08:05:43	FL070	0.3	7	600	2	330	0.10				88		
08:06:43	FL080	0.3	7	600	2	355	0.10						Old PCASP heater on
08:09:50	FL090	0.3	7	500	2	290	0.10				89		
08:10:47	FL100	0.3	7	550	1.5	260	0.10						
08:11:43	FL110	0.3	7	500	1.5	280	0.10						
08:12:50	FL120	0.3	7	525	1.5	320	0.10						
08:14:07	FL130	0.1	7	200	1	100	0.10						
08:15:00	FL140	0.1	7	100	1	50	0.13				90		
08:16:01	FL150	0.1	7	100	1.5	50	0.15						
08:16:55	FL160	0.1	7	100	1.5	30	0.10						
08:18:30	FL170	0.1	7	100	0.4	35	0.08						Heaters on
08:21:10	FL180			100	0.4	30	0.08						
08:22:15	FL190			100	0.5	40	0.08						Old PCASP ch1 noisy
08:22:18	FL200			100	0.4	30	0.08						
08:23:15	FL210			90	0.4	20	0.08						
08:24:10	FL220			90	0.4	20	0.06						
08:25:10	FL230			80	0.4	20	0.06						
08:26:07	FL240			50	0.3	15	0.06						End of Profile
08:55:00													Old and New PCASP very noisy
09:04:00													Heaters off

Post flight

Instrument	Diagnostics		Brief report on instrument performance
PCASP (old)	Vref:	Unknown	Ch1 noise at high level, extreme on transit back at FL240
	Flow:	0.7	
2DC	El#1:	-1.5	
	El#32:	-1.5	
PCASP SPP-200	Ref V:	7.65	Noisy ch1 and sometimes other channels
	Flow:	1.16	
CDP	Laser V:	4.41	Higher laser voltage once cold
FFSSP	Ref V:	3.5	
SID 3	Laser V:	N/a	
Rack Equipment		1.2GB	Please note SEADAS disk space remaining.

Flight:

B442

KEY

Not Fitted

Fitted, Not Operated

Duff Data

Minor Problem

OK

Thermometers

Cabin Temperature:

Heimann:

Deiced Temp:

Non-deiced Temp:

Hygrometers

FWVS:

Buck CR2:

General Eastern:

Johnson Williams:

Nevzorov:

Total Water Probe:

Cameras

Downward Facing:

Forward Facing:

Rearward Facing:

Upward Facing:

Navigation + Aircraft

Cruciform GPS:

GIN Applanix:

INU Honeywell:

Radar Altimeter:

RVSM IAS:

RVSM Static Pressure:

XR5 GPS:

Misc Core

HORACE:

AMTG:

AVAPS:

Cabin Pressure:

Printer:

S9 Static Pressure:

Satcom C:

Satcom H (VIRC):

Turb Centre-Static:

Turb Left Right:

Turb Up-Down:

Turb Horizontal Chk:

Turb Vertical Chk:

Weather Radar:

DLUs:

DLU AERACK:

DLU BBR Lower:

DLU BBR Upper:

DLU Core Chem:

DLU Core Consoles:

DLU Port Aft:

DLU Port Fwd:

DLU Stbd Fwd:

Radiometers

Lower:

BBR (clear) Lower:

BBR (IR) Lower:

BBR (red) Lower:

Upper:

BBR (clear) Upper:

BBR (IR) Upper:

BBR (red) Upper:

ARIES:

DEIMOS:

IR Camera:

JNO2 Lower:

JNO2 Upper:

JO1D Lower:

JO1D Upper:

MARSS:

SHIMS Lower:

SHIMS Upper:

SWS:

TAFTS:

Cloud Probes

2DC:

2DP:

FFSSP:

PCASP:

PCASP SPP-200:

2DS:

ADA:

CAPS:

CCN:

CDP (fuselage):

CDP (Canister):

CIP 100 (PIP):

CIP 25 (CIP):

CPI:

CVI (Inlet):

CVI PCASP-X:

CVI Ly-A Hygro:

FSSP (UMan):

SID1:

SID2:

SID3:

Aerosol

CPC 3025A:

CPC 3786 H2O:

Filters 47mm:

Filters 90mm:

Neph - Dry:

Neph - Wet:

PSAP:

AMS:

CPC (AMS):

SMPS (AMS):

CPC 3010A (CVI):

INC:

Mini-LIDAR:

SP2:

UHSAS:

VACC:

Chemistry

CO Aerolaser 5002:

NOx TE42C:

Ozone TE49C:

Ozone TE49:

SO2 TE43C:

TDLAS (NIR) CH4:

TDLAS (NIR) CO2:

FAGE:

Formaldehyde:

NOx FAAM:

NOxy:

ORAC:

PAN:

PERCA:

Peroxide:

PTRMS:

TDLAS (1C):

WAS Bags:

WAS Bottles:

Misc Non-Core

CASI/ATM:

LIDAR (big):

LTI:

SAW Hygrometer:

ARIES flight log

Flight:

B442

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Date: 30/Apr/09 Operator(s): S. Bacon

Res: 1

Gain A: 2 B: 2

Loc./Notes: MEVEX: Ship wake

Scans: either "[IGMs][co-adds]", or "[stop DRS time]" if in start/stop, or "[macro name]". View: mirror angle.

DRS time	Flt ptrn	Scans	View	Shtr	HBB	CBB	Comments
0250	—						Power on Ok.
0500	TANZ	OFF					
050626	↑	cal	CH	0	81	43	CH cal. micro. ← Don't! Writing to previous flight's folder!
050900	↑	cal	CH	0	81	43	CH cal
054216	↓ 1000ft	cal	CH	0	81	41	CH cal.
054405	↓ 500'	cal	CH	0	81	41	CH cal
054736	700'	cal	CH	0	81	42	CH cal
054900	R11 600'	480x1	N	0	81	42	Nadir
055216		cal	CH	0	81	43	CH cal.
055325	600'	480x1	N	0	81	43	Nadir
055739		cal	CH	0	81	43	CH cal
055905		480x1	N	0	81	44	Nadir
060218		cal	CH	0	81	44	CH cal (not enough time for 2)
060451	R21	cal	CH	0	81	44	CH cal
0606—	1000'	60x1	Z	0	81	45	
060655		480x1	N	0			
061055		cal	CH	0	81	46	CH cal. CBS finds out what?
061224		120x1	Z	0	81	46	Zenith.
061342		360x1	N	0	81	46	Nadir
061645		cal	CH	0	81	46	CH cal
062140	↑	240x1	N				—
062345	3000'	cal	CH	0	81	48	CH cal. turning/diving
062500	R31 3000'	N3min	N	0	81	47	Nadir 3 minutes Not enough time at end of run to fit in Z
		Zenith	Z	0			
064130	5000'	Z1min	Z	0	81	46	Zenith 1min
064323	R41	N3min	N	0	81	46	Nadir 3min
065004		cal	CH	0	81	45	CH cal.
065253	5000'	N3min	N	0	81	44	Nadir 3min end 0702
070554	3000'	N3min	N	0	81	43	Nadir 3min
070910	↓	cal	CH	0	81	43	CH cal.
071209	700'	cal	CH	0	81	43	"

ARIES flight log

Flight: B 442 page 2 of 2

Date: _____ Operator(s): _____ Res: _____ Gain A: B:

Loc./Notes: _____

Scans: either "[IGMs]X[co-adds]", or "[stop DRS time]" if in start/stop, or "[macro name]". View: mirror angle.

DRS time	Flt ptrn	Scans	View	Shtr	HBB	CBB	Comments
07 13 27	600'	480x1	N	0			Nadir
07 14 50		Cal	CH	0	81	44	cal.
07 24 11	5000'	N3min	N	0	81	44	Nadir
07 52 58	5000' ↓	Cal	CH	0	81	42	end 0753 Some fuffing about to reportin (along with a juggle of Scientist running around like headless chickens looking for some god-damned boat) so I might as well run a nadir macro and get my head down for forty winks. CH cal.
08 24 00	FL230	Cal	CH	0	81	41	CH cal.
08 26 00	FL240	360x1	N	0	81	41	Nadir Sande
08 30 44	"	N3min	N	0	81	41	Nadir 3min
08 40 47	"	120x1	Z	0	81	41	Zenith C1 above
08 41 50	"	N3min	N	0	81	41	Nadir 3min
08 53 12	↓?"	Cal	CH	0	81	41	CH

Microwave Radiometers FLIGHT LOG		Date	30/04/09	Flight	B442	log pages
Operator(s)	J Bowles		Campaign	MEVEX		
Departure	Muscat		Arrival	Muscat		

System start

MARSS

Visual pod inspection						Y
Close 3 SSP circuit breakers						•
Close all MARSS circuit breakers						•
FERA on	at time					03:29
Temperature controller initial temps	Ch16	30°C	Ch	30°C	Ch18	30°C
Temperature controller set points		54°C	17	58°C	-20	40°C
MARSS CPU on	at time					03:29
Initial target temperatures	Hot	303.8	Cold	305.9		
Target heating						•
*** CHECK SCAN HEAD CLEAR ***						•
Scanning on (LMD box)	at time					
Scan indication	Monitor			•	Visual	•

Deimos

Close all Deimos circuit breakers						
Turn on Deimos CPU						
*** CHECK SCAN HEAD CLEAR ***						
Start Deimos Software	at time					
Initial target temperatures	Hot		Cold			
Target heating						
Scan indication	Monitor				Visual	
Weather	Cloud		Precip			
	Surface		Pressure			
	Other					

System functionality check

(after initial system warmup, approx 1 hour)

PC to DRS Time error	$t_{PC}=t_{DRS} +$	0	at time	04:42:40		
Brightness temps 'sensible'						•
Target temps	MARSS:	Hot	344.70	Cold	313.16	
	Deimos:	Hot		Cold		
Channel gains 'sensible'	Ch1 A	Ch3 A	Ch1 B	Ch3 B		
	(-)	(-)	(-)	(-)		
	Ch16	Ch17	Ch18	Ch19	Ch20	
	(40-44)	(45-49)	(40-44)	(40-44)	(44-48)	
	37.93	31.07	37.57	40.63	41.24	

Power changeover

Headset on before start						•
Listen to engine start sequence	4, 3, 2, 1.					•
LMD off (3 switches, bottom to top)						•
Exit Deimos Software (x)						
POWER CHANGEOVER						
LMD on (3 switches, top to bottom)	then pushbutton					•
Restart Deimos Software						
System running again	at time					

Flight B442 09:18:11

Heading 262 deg Speed 8 knots Height 0.1kft Press 1006mb

Lat 23°30.0'N Long 58°12.0'E Wind 95 ms-1/ 301 deg

Temp 37.46C Dewpoint 14.54C

From 08:53:00 to now

	Current values		
	STATIC PRESSURE	1006.1	mb
++++	DEICED TRUE AIR TEMP	37.47	deg C
++++	DEW POINT	14.54	deg C

Flight B442 09:18:00

Heading 247 deg Speed 8 knots Height 0.1kft Press 1006mb

Lat 23°30.0'N Long 58°12.0'E Wind 139 ms-1/ 306 deg

Temp 37.38C Dewpoint 14.78C

From 08:53:00 to now

	Current values			
	PRESSURE HEIGHT	0.2	Kft	● All
++++	NEPH BLUE SP	90.53	m-1	○
++++	NEPH GREEN SP	77.68	m-1	○
++++	NEPH RED SP	62.93	m-1	○

Flight B442 08:25:54

Heading 254 deg Speed 313 knots Height 23.9kft Press 393mb

Lat 22°54.0'N Long 62°18.0'E Wind 11 ms-1/ 292 deg

Temp -23.31C Dewpoint -45.93C

From 07:58:59 to now

	Current values		
	STATIC PRESSURE	393.93	mb
++++	DEICED TRUE AIR TEMP	-23.32	deg C
++++	DEW POINT	-45.93	deg C

Flight B442 05:44:59

Heading 164 deg Speed 206 knots Height 0.4kft Press 996mb

Lat 22°18.0'N Long 61°18.0'E Wind 12 ms-1/ 246 deg

Temp 30.76C Dewpoint 18.3C

From 05:20:00 to now

	Current values		
	STATIC PRESSURE	996.54	mb
++++	DEICED TRUE AIR TEMP	30.76	deg C
++++	DEW POINT	18.31	deg C

Flight B442 05:17:22

Heading 109 deg Speed 352 knots Height 20.9kft Press 446mb

Lat 23°24.0'N Long 59°42.0'E Wind 5 ms-1/ 297 deg

Temp -15.85C Dewpoint -35.78C

From 04:30:00 to now

Current values				
●	PRESSURE HEIGHT	21	Kft	● All
++++	NEPH BLUE SP	10.81	m-1	○
++++	NEPH GREEN SP	7.63	m-1	○
++++	NEPH RED SP	6.56	m-1	○

Flight B442 05:17:51

Heading 109 deg Speed 323 knots Height 20.9kft Press 446mb

Lat 23°24.0'N Long 59°42.0'E Wind 4 ms-1/ 307 deg

Temp -15.55C Dewpoint -36.19C

From 04:30:00 to now

	Current values		
	STATIC PRESSURE	446.7	mb
++++	DEICED TRUE AIR TEMP	-15.55	deg C
++++	DEW POINT	-36.19	deg C

Flight B442 05:44:50

Heading 175 deg Speed 204 knots Height 0.2kft Press 1002mb

Lat 22°18.0'N Long 61°12.0'E Wind 10 ms-1/ 247 deg

Temp 30.74C Dewpoint 20.11C

From 05:20:00 to now

Current values			
+++++ PRESSURE HEIGHT	0.29	Kft	● All
+++++ NEPH BLUE SP	107.18	m-1	○
+++++ NEPH GREEN SP	101.46	m-1	○
+++++ NEPH RED SP	98.93	m-1	○